

Studies on Hydrolysis of Alkoxy and Alkoxyacyloxysilanes

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Studies on the hydrolysis of tetra*isopropoxy*silane show that it is not hydrolysed even in presence of acids or alkalis. This appears to be due to steric factors brought about by the ramification of the alkoxy group. However, with the gradual replacement of the *isopropoxy* by *acyloxy* groups, the hydrolysis reaction became facile so much so that the di*isopropoxydiacyloxy*silane was hydrolysed with ease and the *isopropoxy* content could be estimated easily by chromate oxidation.

While tetrachlorosilane is highly reactive and hydrolyses immediately in contact with water, Sidgwick¹ has proposed that this hydrolysis takes place through the initial coordination of a water molecule followed by the loss of hydrogen chloride.

The process of hydrolysis of organohalosilanes has attracted considerable attention recently as a method for obtaining silanols, siloxanes and even alkoxy silanes. Since the hydrolysis reactions are much too fast and very complicated, it has been difficult to study the mechanism of the process.

In the case of alkoxy silanes, those ones are hydrolysed quickly which are brought into solution. In the neutral medium hydrolysis is generally slow, but it is catalysed by acids or alkalis. In these hydrolysis reactions of alkoxy silanes, the Si-O bonds appear to undergo cleavage and the approach of the hydrolysing agent is hindered by the bulky groups attached either to silicon or oxygen.

Several workers have carried out the hydrolysis of silicon compounds and valuable results have been obtained.

Studies have been carried out in these laboratories on the hydrolysis of alkoxy and alkoxyacyloxysilanes and it has been found that while tetra*ethoxy*silane is easily hydrolysable and ethanol can be quantitatively removed from it, the next member tetra*isopropoxy*silane stands in marked contrast with the above and *isopropanol* cannot be removed from it by subjecting it even to vigorous hydrolysis.

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1. Sidgwick, N. V., "Electronic Theory of Valency," The University Press Oxford, 1927, p. 157.

It is interesting to note that the hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane by refluxing it with benzene and water or even by benzene, water and a little caustic soda pellet failed to set free the isopropanol, as the same could not be detected in the azeotropic mixture with benzene obtained by fractionation. Contrary to the expected behaviour, tetraisopropoxysilane could be obtained back in approximately 100% yield by distillation when all benzene and water had been fractionated out from the reaction flask.

Acidic hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane by concentrated sulphuric acid was helpful only to a slight extent and here also, even by refluxing tetraisopropoxysilane with benzene and a little concentrated sulphuric acid, only very little isopropanol could be liberated.

However, it was observed that hydrofluoric acid was of greater help and could effect hydrolysis to a greater extent than sulphuric acid and as the quantity of the former was increased, the proportion of isopropanol liberated also increased, but beyond a certain stage, the estimation again became difficult owing to the etching of the glass container and the hydrolysis could not be pushed upto the final stage.

The same results were obtained not only with tetraisopropoxysilane, but even with triisopropoxymonoacyloxysilane, in which case also low values of isopropanol were obtained in the azeotrope against the calculated value of 3 moles, by refluxing the compound with benzene and water and then by fractionating out benzene. On the other hand, diisopropoxy-diacyloxysilane was hydrolysed by water containing a little caustic soda in refluxing benzene and two moles of isopropanol could be easily fractionated out with benzene azeotropically.

Since the ethoxy content of tetraethoxysilane could be estimated easily and so also the isopropoxy content, in diisopropoxydiacyloxysilane and since it was not possible to estimate the isopropoxy content either in tri-isopropoxy-monoacyloxysilane or in tetraisopropoxysilane, it is obvious that as the number of isopropoxy groups increases from two to three or four, the compounds obtained assume stabler character towards hydrolytic reagents and estimation of the isopropoxy content in them becomes difficult. This can be ascribed to the steric factors brought about by the ramification of the alkoxy group.

These observations are of great interest in view of the hydrolysable nature of the organic derivatives of silicon.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus: All-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used throughout and fractionations were carried out in a column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total condensation variable take-off still-head.

Materials: Tetraethoxysilane (B.D.H., A.R.) was fractionated and the fraction between 168-169.6° was collected. It was further confirmed by the analyses of silicon and ethoxy contents.

Tetraisopropoxy, triisopropoxymonoacyloxy and diisopropoxydiacyloxysilanes were prepared^a and purified by distillation under reduced pressure and were confirmed by the analyses of their silicon and alkoxy contents.

Analytical Methods: Silicon, ethoxy and isopropoxy contents were estimated by methods already communicated*.

1. *Hydrolysis of tetraethoxysilane.*—To tetraethoxysilane (3.71 g) was added benzene (6.50 g) and water (4.62 g) and after refluxing the contents for about 1½ hours (bath temperature 110–120°), when fractionation was started, an azeotrope (11.0 g) was fractionated out in course of about 2 hours at 88°.

Found: ethanol, 3.10 g; 4 moles require 3.28 g.

Afterwards a white slimy substance (2.56 g) had remained in the flask.

2. *Hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane.*—A little weighed tetraisopropoxysilane (0.0268 g) was added to a known volume of standard potassium dichromate taken in a microconical flask and after allowing to stand for 2 hours at the room temperature, excess potassium dichromate was titrated iodometrically.

(Found: C_3H_7O , 10.85. $Si(OC_3H_7)_4$ requires C_3H_7O , 89.39%.)

3. *Alkaline hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane.*—To tetraisopropoxysilane (0.0312 g) was added a caustic soda pellet and then left for about 20 minutes. A few drops of conc. H_2SO_4 were then added and finally a known volume of standard chromic acid. After keeping the contents for 20 hours, the unused chromic acid was titrated iodometrically. (Found: C_3H_7O , 35.82. $Si(OC_3H_7)_4$ requires C_3H_7O , 89.39%.)

4. *Acidic hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane.*—Tetraisopropoxysilane (0.0284 g) was added to a known volume of standard chromic acid to which was then added 0.5 ml of a 40% solution of hydrofluoric acid and after allowing to stand for about 2 hours, the unused chromic acid was titrated iodometrically.

(Found: C_3H_7O , 25.95. $Si(OC_3H_7)_4$ requires, C_3H_7O , 89.39%.)

With varying amounts of H_2F_2 , the results are as follows:

$(C_3H_7O)_4Si$ (g)	Vol. of H_2F_2 (ml)	C_3H_7O (%)
0.0319	2.5	55.46
0.0364	3.5	62.20
0.0300	5.0	65.86

With quantities of H_2F_2 greater than 5 ml, etching of the glass container started taking place and estimation became difficult.

5. *Hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane by refluxing.*—Tetraisopropoxysilane was subjected to hydrolysis by refluxing it with water in presence of benzene.

(A) A thin white film was formed on the surface of the contents obtained by mixing the silane (2.0 g) to benzene (5.95 g) and water (16.0 g) and leaving it overnight. The solution remained almost clear even after refluxing the whole mixture for about

2 hours. A small pellet of caustic soda was added and the solution was then distilled when two fractions were collected.

- (i) 5.0 g between 81 and 84°
- (ii) 16.0 g between 96 and 98°

Both these fractions had no isopropanol.

(B) Benzene (41.9 g) and water (4.9 g) were successively added to tetraisopropoxy-silane (5.09 g) and after refluxing for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours under a column, the contents were slowly fractionated into two parts.

- (i) 24.0 g upto 69.3°
- (ii) 21.0 g between 69.3 and 76°

Both these fractions had no isopropanol and did not reduce chromic acid.

After fractionation, when the clear contents (6.45 g) were distilled, few drops of a colourless liquid came at 80°. Finally a colourless solution (3.90 g) distilled at 184°. (Found: Si, 10.60. Si (OC₃H₇)₄ requires Si, 10.60%).

A little white solid together with a few drops of a colourless liquid (0.7 g) remained undistilled.

6. *Alkaline hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane by refluxing.*—Into tetraisopropoxy-silane (3.18 g) was added benzene (23.73 g), water (3.49 g) and then two pellets of caustic soda and after refluxing the solution for 2 hours, the contents were cooled. A thin white film was formed at the surface. There was no change on keeping the solution overnight. On fractionation two portions were collected.

- (i) 11.0 g between 68 and 70°
- (ii) 13.0 g between 70 and 73°

Both these fractions had no isopropanol. The colourless contents (4.9 g) on distillation first gave few drops of a colourless liquid at 80° and a liquid (2.4 g) at 183°. (Found: Si, 10.60. Si (OC₃H₇)₄ requires Si, 10.60%).

A very little white deposit had remained in the flask.

7. *Acidic hydrolysis of tetraisopropoxysilane by refluxing.*—To tetraisopropoxysilane (1.58 g) was added benzene (6.87 g) and conc. H₂SO₄ (0.34 g) and on shaking the solution, immediately a white deposit was formed which later settled down. After refluxing the contents for an hour under the column, when fractionation was started, a colourless liquid came at 65° and after about 5 minutes, the temperature of the distilling liquid started falling and went on falling even when the bath temperature had been raised to 140°. In course of an hour a colourless liquid (6.32 g) had been fractionated out. (Found: isopropanol, 0.65 g; 4 moles require 1.43 g).

A white powder together with some charred matter was left in the flask.

8. *Hydrolysis of triisopropoxymonobutylsilyl silane.*—The triisopropoxymonobutyl-silyl silane employed had the following analysis: (Found: Si, 9.53; (C₃H₇O)₃ Si (OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃) requires Si, 9.59.

To the silane (1.88 g) was added benzene (8.43 g) and water (1.27 g). On vigorously shaking the contents after mixing, a white precipitate was obtained. The contents were refluxed under the column for about 2 hours (bath temperature 115-120°) and on fractionation the temperature of the distilling liquid was constant at 65°, but after 10 minutes, it started falling even when the bath temperature had been raised to about 140°. In course of about 1½ hours, a colourless liquid (7.5 g) had been collected. (Found: isopropanol, 0.823 g; 3 moles require 1.159 g).

After fractionation, the contents (2.30 g) were a white alimy substance together with a colourless liquid. On subjecting it to reduced pressure distillation, nothing was obtained even at 230°/0.1-0.3 mm. A little white powder was left as the residue.

9. *Hydrolysis of diisopropoxydibutyroxy silane.*—The diisopropoxydibutyroxy silane employed gave the following results on analysis: (Found: Si, 8.76; C₃H₇Oⁱ, 36.56. (C₃H₇Oⁱ)₂ Si (OOC. CH₂CH₂CH₃)₂ requires Si, 8.75; C₃H₇Oⁱ, 36.86%).

To diisopropoxydibutyroxy silane (1.02 g) was added benzene (8.03 g) and water (2.78 g). On shaking a white suspension had appeared; but no precipitate. Then about half pellet of caustic soda was added in it and after about 5 minutes, a precipitate was formed. After refluxing the contents for about an hour under the column (bath temperature 110-120°), when fractionation was started, an azeotrope (7.34 g) was obtained between 66.5° and 68.5°, in course of about 1½ hours.

(Found: isopropanol, 0.30 g; 2 moles require 0.37 g).